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Influence of Cassava Peel Ash on Bruce Marshall Properties of Asphalt Concrete under Submergence

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ABSTRACT

The use of agricultural waste materials in highway construction has gained attention due to growing concerns about environmental sustainability and material scarcity. This study evaluates the influence of cassava peel ash (CPA) as a mineral filler on Bruce Marshall properties of asphalt concrete under submergence. CPA was incorporated at varying rates (0%, 2.5%, 5%, 7.5% and 10%) by weight of aggregate, and the resulting mixes were tested for stability, flow, density, air voids (V_a), voids in mineral aggregate (VMA), and voids filled with asphalt (VFA). Results revealed that the inclusion of CPA up to 7.5% enhanced all Marshall properties by exceeding its minimum specification when submerged in water for up to 3 days. With an overall improvement of approximately: 49.34 - 59.60% in stability, 9% in flow, 0.8% in density, 20.93 - 26.02% in V_a , 3.37 - 3.7% VMA and 10.80 - 11.11% in VFA as compared to the control mix, while higher percentages beyond 7.5% led to a decline in all Marshall properties due to excess CPA content. The optimal CPA replacement level was identified at 7.5%, and it is suitable when the pavement is under submergence for not more than 3 days. These findings demonstrate that cassava peel ash is a viable supplementary material for improving asphalt performance while promoting sustainable waste management practices in tropical regions.

Keywords: CPA, Bruce Marshall Properties, Submerged Asphalt Concrete.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid increase in vehicular traffic and environmental degradation has accelerated the search for sustainable materials in road construction. Conventional bituminous mixtures rely on mineral fillers such as limestone dust, which contribute significantly to cost and environmental impact due to quarrying and carbon emissions (Al-Hdabi, 2016). Meanwhile, agricultural by-products such as cassava peel abundantly generated in tropical regions like Africa, South America, and Asia, pose serious waste disposal challenges (Ettu *et al.*, 2013). Converting cassava peel into ash for use as a partial filler in asphalt concrete not only minimizes environmental pollution but also enhances resource efficiency and cost savings (Osu *et al.*, 2020).

The Bruce Marshall method remains a fundamental approach for evaluating the performance of asphalt mixes, particularly their stability and flow characteristics (Khanna & Justo, 2008). The method measures the resistance of bituminous mixtures to plastic deformation under loading, representing the mixture's ability to withstand traffic stresses. However, the submergence of pavements, caused by poor drainage and heavy rainfall, is a major concern in tropical climates, often leading to stripping and loss of adhesion between bitumen and aggregates (Oluwasola *et al.*, 2015). Jasim & Joni, (2022) highlighted moisture as a significant factor in fatigue life degradation, emphasizing that moisture infiltration accelerates damage in asphalt concrete by weakening adhesion between aggregates and the binder. The incorporation of pozzolanic materials like cassava peel ash could mitigate such moisture susceptibility through micro-filling effects and improved interfacial bonding (Akinyemi & Olatunji, 2014; Obilade, 2014; Amadi-Oparaeli & Onyekaba, 2026).

However, limited research exists on the performance of CPA-modified asphalt concrete under submerged conditions. Moisture damage is a significant concern for asphalt pavements, leading to reduced strength, increased cracking, and ultimately, pavement failure. This research therefore investigates the influence of cassava peel ash on the Bruce Marshall properties of asphalt concrete under submergence, using CPA as a partial replacement for conventional fillers. The study aims to determine the optimal CPA content that yields maximum strength and durability while maintaining acceptable properties in line with Marshall mix design criteria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Agricultural Waste Utilization in Pavement

The integration of agricultural and industrial by-products into asphalt mixes aligns with sustainable pavement development goals (Ongel & Hugener, 2015). Studies have demonstrated that ashes derived from materials such as rice husk, coconut shell, and palm kernel shell improve asphalt performance due to their fine particle size and pozzolanic characteristics (Jaya *et al.*, 2017; Okafor & Okonkwo, 2019). These materials enhance the interfacial bond between binder and aggregate, thereby reducing moisture susceptibility (Al-Hdabi, 2016). Amadi-Oparaeli *et al.*, (2020) examined the effect of periwinkle shell ash on the stability and elastic properties of modified asphalt concrete and discovered that the properties of the modified asphalt concrete were better than that of conventional concrete at 2.5% periwinkle shell ash by weight of aggregate. Ashes from agricultural by-products have been utilized in various ways in pavement engineering. For instance, Onyekaba *et al.*, (2025) incorporated Burnt Bamboo Leafs (BBL) as substitute for Portland cement in soil

stabilization at 3%, 6%, 9%, 12% and 15% by dry weight and discovered that BBL increased Optimum Moisture Content (OMC), reduced Maximum Dry Density (MDD), and enhanced CBR; Amadi-Oparaeli & Otto, (2022) used CPA as void filler to improve the volumetric properties of asphalt concrete mixtures.

Cassava peel ash, being rich in silica (SiO_2) and alumina (Al_2O_3), has been reported to possess cementitious properties that make it suitable for partial substitution of mineral fillers in asphalt (Ettu *et al.*, 2013; Osu *et al.*, 2020). The calcination process of cassava peel between 600°C and 700°C converts organic matter into reactive oxides, capable of improving the packing density and durability of asphalt concrete (Akinyemi & Olatunji, 2014).

Marshall Stability and Flow Properties

The Marshall stability of an asphalt mixture reflects its load-bearing capacity, while flow indicates its plastic deformation under load (Khanna & Justo, 2008). Both parameters are influenced by binder content, aggregate gradation, and filler characteristics. A balance between stability and flow ensures adequate flexibility and resistance to rutting (Arafat *et al.*, 2020). Moisture damage in asphalt concrete refers to the degradation in mechanical properties (stability, flow) under load, deformation, resulting from the presence of water. It shows mechanisms such as weakening of binder-aggregate adhesion also known as stripping, softening of binder, swelling, formation of pore pressures, loss of

stiffness etc. (Liang *et al.*, 2023). The optimum values of stability and flow are as shown in table 1 below.

Volumetric Parameters

Percentage air void (V_a), voids in mineral aggregate (VMA), voids filled with asphalt (VFA) and density are indicators of internal air space within the mix. Optimum values of V_a (3 - 5%) and VFA (65 - 75%) ensure proper bitumen coating and air voids balance, critical for moisture resistance and durability (Mohammed *et al.*, 2019), as seen in table 1 below. According to Fernandes *et al.*, (2017), moisture infiltrates asphalt pavements through air voids, weakening the asphalt–aggregate bond and reducing mixture density. Karsono *et al.*, (2025) revealed that aggregate gradation affects how tightly packed the aggregates can be, and therefore directly influences VMA. Indriani *et al.*, (2024) carried out a study in Indonesia using conventional asphalt concrete mixture subjected to continuous immersion for 1, 2, and 3 days, revealed that VFB decreased as immersion time increased ($\approx 77.05\%$ after 1 day, $\approx 73.94\%$ after 2 days, and $\approx 73.07\%$ after 3 days). The density of the compacted mixture, usually expressed as a percentage of theoretical maximum specific gravity (% G_{mm}), indicates the level of compaction achieved and correlates strongly with pavement service life (Mogawer *et al.*, 2011). Density of a compacted asphalt concrete mixture should range between 2200kg/m^3 to 2500kg/m^3 (Tarefder & Makar, 2015; ASTM D2726-17, 2017).

Table 1: Marshall Mix Design Criteria (Asphalt Institute MS-2, 2014).

Marshall Method Criteria	Heavy Traffic Surface & Base	
	Min.	Max.
Compaction, number of blows on each end of specimen	75	
Stability, N (Ib)	8006 (1800)	-
Flow, 0.25 mm (0.01 in)	8	14
Percent Air Voids	3	5

Percent Voids in Mineral Aggregate (VMA)	See table 2	
Percent Voids Filled with Asphalt (VFA)	65	75

Table 2: Minimum Percent Voids in Mineral Aggregate (VMA)
(Asphalt Institute MS-2, 2014).

Nominal Maximum Particle Size	Minimum VMA (percent)			
	Design Air Voids (percent)			
mm	in.	3.0	4.0	5.0
1.18	No. 16	21.5	22.5	23.5
2.36	No. 8	19.0	20.0	21.0
4.75	No. 4	16.0	17.0	18.0
9.5	3/8	14.0	15.0	16.0
12.5	1/2	13.0	14.0	15.0
19.0	3/4	12.0	13.0	14.0
25.0	1.0	11.0	12.0	13.0
37.5	1.5	10.0	11.0	12.0
50	2.0	9.5	10.5	11.5
63	2.5	9.0	10.0	11.0

Effects of Pozzolanic Additives on Submerged Asphalt Mixes

Submergence significantly affects the durability of asphalt pavements, particularly through water-induced damage known as stripping, which leads to debonding of bitumen from aggregate surfaces (Oluwasola *et al.*, 2015). Several researchers have examined the role of pozzolanic fillers in enhancing submerged asphalt performance. For instance, Oluwasola *et al.*, (2015) found that rice husk ash improved water resistance and stability in submerged conditions. Similarly, Arafat *et al.*, (2020) observed that palm kernel shell ash increased Marshall stability and tensile strength ratio due to its micro-filling ability.

CPA has shown comparable potential due to its siliceous composition, which promotes binder-aggregate adhesion and reduces permeability (Ettu *et al.*, 2013; Akinyemi & Olatunji, 2014). The high silica and potassium oxide content contributes to improved cohesion and reduced stripping potential (Obilade, 2014). In the dataset provided, CPA

replacement up to 7.5% resulted in higher stability and density values, signifying improved load resistance under submerged conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials Sampling

The materials employed in this study consist of sharp sand, categorized as fine aggregate, and granite, classified as coarse aggregate. The maximum particle sizes for these materials are confined to 4.75 mm for the fine aggregate and 12.7 mm for the coarse aggregate. Both categories of aggregate were procured at Mile III building materials market, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. Cassava peels were sourced from local agricultural producers in Kaani, located within the Khana Local Government Area of Rivers State. Furthermore, the asphalt cement was obtained from the Nigerian Ports Authority, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.

Classification of Materials

Classification tests were conducted for all materials that constitute the asphalt concrete as follows:

- Specific Gravity of granite was obtained in accordance with ASTM C97/C97M-23: 2023 as 2.6.
- Specific Gravity of sand was obtained in accordance with ASTM C128-23: 2023 as 2.7.
- Specific Gravity of CPA was obtained in accordance with ASTM C128-23: 2023 as 2.15.
- Specific Gravity of bitumen was obtained in accordance with ASTM D70/D70M-23: 2023 as 0.95.
- Penetration of bitumen was obtained in accordance with ASTM D5/D5M-20: 2020 as 69.
- Viscosity of bitumen was obtained in accordance with ASTM D2171/D2171M-22: 2022 as 75s.
- Softening point of bitumen was obtained in accordance with ASTM D36/D36M-24: 2024 as 52.75⁰C.

Table 3: Particle size distribution for sand [ASTM C136 – 01, (2001)].

Sieve No. (mm)	Mass Retained	Percentage on Sieve	Percentage Retained	Percentage Passing
4.75	13	1.1	0.3	98.9
3.35	16	1.3	1.2	97.6
2.36	29	2.4	3.2	95.2
2.00	46	3.8	4.3	91.3
1.18	100	8.3	11.8	83.0
0.850	259	21.6	21.9	61.4
0.600	476	39.7	58.8	21.8
0.425	105	8.8	78.1	13.0
0.300	120	10.0	88.7	3.0
0.150	25	2.1	99.4	0.9
0.075	9	0.8	99.8	0.2
Pan	1	0.1	99.8	0.1
Sum	1198	99.8		

Table 4: Particle size distribution for granite [ASTM C136 - 01, (2001)].

Sieve No. (mm)	Mass Retained	Percentage on Sieve	Percentage Passing
25.4	0	0.0	100.0
19.0	0	0.0	100.0
12.5	106.5	8.9	91.1
9.5	573.6	47.8	43.3
6.7	317.8	26.5	16.8
4.75	99.1	8.3	8.6
3.35	60.8	5.1	3.5
2.36	5.3	0.4	3.1
1.18	4.8	0.4	2.7
0.425	10.2	0.9	1.8
0.3	0	0.0	1.8
0.075	15	1.3	0.6
Sum	1193.1	99.9	99.4

Sample Preparation

Asphalt concrete mixes were prepared using the Marshall mix design method. CPA was used as mineral filler at 0%, 2.5%, 5%, 7.5%, and 10% by weight of aggregate. Each mix was prepared at the optimum bitumen content (O.B.C)

determined through preliminary trials as shown in table 5 and equation 1 below, by determining the bitumen content at maximum stability (x), bitumen content at maximum density (y) and bitumen content at medium limits of air voids (i.e. at 5% air voids) (z).

$$O.B.C = 1/3 (x+y+z) \tag{1}$$

Table 5: Summary of preliminary mix design properties used to obtain optimum binder content (OBC).

Bitumen (%)	Stability (N)	Density (kg/m ³)	Flow (0.25mm)	V _a (%)	VMA (%)	VFA (%)
4.0	8240	2210	6.4	5.29	12.26	56.85
4.5	9900	2219	6.8	4.12	12.00	65.67
5.0	11340	2230	7.2	2.91	11.70	75.13
5.5	12320	2246	8.0	1.48	11.23	86.82
6.0	10800	2236	8.8	1.23	11.50	89.30

Aggregates and filler were first preheated to 160 °C, while bitumen was heated to 150 °C for mixing. The components were thoroughly mixed to ensure homogeneity and compacted using 75 blows per face with a Marshall hammer as specified in ASTM D6926. Thereafter, the samples were cured at room temperature for 24 hours before immersion and testing.

To simulate field submergence conditions, the specimens were immersed in water at 60 °C for 24 hours before testing. Marshall stability and flow were determined using ASTM D1559 -20: (2020), while volumetric properties (V_a, VMA, and VFA) were calculated using (Asphalt Institute MS-2, 2014).

Preliminary design properties

i. Maximum specific gravity of compacted mixture (G_{mm})

This is which is obtained as:

$$G_{mm} = \frac{W_{ca}+W_{fa}+W_b+W_{mod.}}{\frac{W_{ca}}{G_{ca}} + \frac{W_{fa}}{G_{fa}} + \frac{W_b}{G_b} + \frac{W_{mod.}}{G_{mod.}}} \tag{2}$$

where:

W_{ca} is the weight of coarse aggregate in the total mix

W_{fa} is the weight of fine aggregate in the total mix

W_b is the weight of bitumen in the total mix

W_{mod.} is the weight of modifier in the total mix

G_{ca} is the specific gravity of coarse aggregate

G_{fa} is the specific gravity of fine aggregate

G_b is the specific gravity of bitumen.

G_{mod.} is the specific gravity of modifier.

ii. Bulk Specific Gravity of the Mix (G_{mb})

The bulk specific gravity of the mix was obtained from equation 2 below:

$$G_{mb} = \frac{W_a}{W_a + W_w} \quad (3)$$

where:

W_a is the weight of mix in air

W_w is the weight of mix fully submerged in water

NOTE: $W_a - W_w$ gives the volume of the mix.

iii. Volume of Bitumen (V_b)

The volume of bitumen (V_b) is the percentage of volume of bitumen to the total volume of the mix, and it is given as:

$$V_b = \frac{\frac{W_b}{G_b}}{\frac{W_{ca} + W_{fa} + W_b}{G_{mb}}} \quad (4)$$

Parameters are as defined above.

Mix Design Properties

The following are the mix design properties of the asphalt concrete mixture:

i. Stability of Mix (N)

The stability values were obtained directly from the stabilimeter machine.

ii. Flow of Mix (mm)

The flow values were obtained directly from the flow gauge attached to the stabilimeter.

iii. Density of Mix (kg/m^3)

The density of the mix was obtained from equation 4 as stated below:

$$\%G_{mm} = \left(\frac{G_{mb}}{G_{mm}} \right) \times 100 \quad (5)$$

iv. Percent Air Voids (V_a)

The percent air voids was obtained from equation 5 below:

$$V_a = \left(\frac{G_{mm} - G_{mb}}{G_{mm}} \right) \times 100 \quad (6)$$

where:

G_{mb} is the bulk specific gravity of the compacted mix.

G_{mm} is maximum specific gravity of the compacted mix

v. Voids in Mineral Aggregate (VMA)

The voids in Mineral Aggregate (VMA) was obtained from equation 6 below:

$$VMA = V_a + V_b \quad (7)$$

where:

V_a is the air voids in the mix

V_b is the volume of asphalt

vi. Voids Filled with Asphalt (VFA)

The voids filled with asphalt (VFA) is obtained from equation 7 below:

$$VFA = \left(\frac{VMA - V_a}{VMA} \right) \times 100 \tag{8}$$

Parameters are as defined above

Table 5: Schedule for Aggregate Blending.

Sieve (in.)	Sieve (mm)	Specification Limit	% passing Aggregate A (Gravel)	% passing Aggregate B (Sand)	Mix Proportion (0.57A+0.43B)	Tolerance
3/4"	19.1	100	100.0	100.0	100.0	±6
1/2"	12.7	76-92	90.4	100.0	94.0	±6
3/8"	9.52	64-79	41.6	100.0	63.8	±5
No. 4	4.75	40-60	17.1	98.9	48.2	±5
No.10	1.18	23-37	8.6	83.0	36.9	±4
No. 40	0.425	7-20	6.3	13.0	8.8	±4
No. 80	0.300	5-13	4.8	3.0	4.1	±3
No. 200	0.075	3-8	3.8	0.2	2.4	±1.5
Filler						

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Effect of CPA Content on Stability

Marshall Stability is a representation of the asphalt concrete mixture’s resistance to deformation under traffic load. The graphs

shown in figures 1a to 1b represents the stability of the asphalt concrete mixture modified with CPA and submerged in water for a period of 0 to 5 day(s).

Fig. 1a: Effect of submergence on stability

Figure 1a shows a progressive decrease in stability of the compacted asphalt concrete mixtures, with increase in submergence period for all CPA modified samples. This is so because it has been proven that moisture infiltrates asphalt pavements through air voids, weakening the asphalt-aggregate bond and reduce mixture

Fig. 1b: Effect of CPA on stability

density, hence, leading to decrease of the overall stiffness of the mix (Fernandes *et al.*, 2017). However, from figure 1b, it was observed that the presence of CPA improved the stability of the compacted mixture by an increase from 9380N at 0% CPA to 14056N at 7.5% CPA for none submergence period, 9040N at 0% CPA to

13500N at 7.5% CPA for 1 day submergence period, 8144N at 0% CPA to 12828N at 7.5% CPA for 2 days submergence period, 7960N at 0% CPA to 12704N at 7.5% CPA for 3 days submergence period, 7424N at 0% CPA to 11384N at 7.5% CPA for 4 days submergence period and 6904N at 0% CPA to 7896N at 7.5% CPA for 5 days submergence period. This trend suggests improved interfacial bonding and stiffness due to the fine pozzolanic ash filling micro-voids and enhancing binder-aggregate adhesion (Oluwasola *et al.*, 2015; Arafat *et al.*, 2020). At 10% CPA, the stability dropped, indicating that excessive CPA content may hinder binder coating uniformity and induce brittleness (Osu *et al.*, 2020). This behavior corroborates findings by Mohammed *et al.*, (2019), who reported optimum filler

content between 5-8% for agricultural ashes in asphalt mixes. Furthermore, it was observed that the stability values for all CPA modified samples submerged for up to 3 days met the Marshall criteria as specified in table 1, with an improvement of 49.34 - 59.60% as compared to the control. It can therefore be said that CPA modified asphalt concrete should not be applied for pavements under moisture submergence for more than 3 days.

Effect of CPA Content on Flow

Flow is a measure of how much asphalt concrete sample deforms when subjected to traffic loading. The graphs shown in figures 2a to 2b represent the flow of the asphalt concrete mixture modified with CPA and submerged in water for a period of 0 to 5 day(s).

Fig. 2a: Effect of submergence on flow.

Fig. 2b: Effect of CPA on flow.

Figure 2a shows a progressive increase in flow with increase in submergence period. This is because the presence of water is showcased by the mechanism of stripping, softening of binder, loss of stiffness etc. (Liang, *et al.*, 2023). On the other hand, figure 2b shows a gradual decrease in flow from 9.12mm at 0% CPA to 8.28mm at 7.5% CPA for none submergence period, 9.72mm at 0% CPA to 8.84mm at 7.5% CPA for 1 day submergence period, 10.44mm at 0% CPA to 9.48mm at 7.5% CPA for 2 days submergence period,

10.60mm at 0% CPA to 9.64mm at 7.5% CPA for 3 days submergence period, 10.88mm at 0% CPA to 9.88mm at 7.5% CPA for 4 days submergence period and 11.72mm at 0% CPA to 10.68mm at 7.5% CPA for 5 days submergence period.

This reduction in flow is an indication of enhanced stiffness of the mixture by the inclusion of CPA content up to 7.5%; beyond which the flow began to increase, giving a signal of reduced stiffness. Irrespective of the reduction in stiffness of

the mix at 10% CPA content, it was observed that the presence of CPA in the mixture improved the flow by approximately 9% as compared to the control, for all CPA modified samples submerged in water. Also, the flow values fell within acceptable Marshall range of 8mm to 14mm as shown in table 1 above.

Effect of CPA Content on Density

Fig. 3a: Effect of submergence on density.

Figure 3a shows a progressive decrease in density of the compacted asphalt concrete mixtures, with increase in submergence period for all CPA modified samples. This is so because it has been proven that moisture infiltrates asphalt pavements through air voids, weakening the asphalt–aggregate bond and reducing mixture density (Fernandes *et al.*, 2017). However, from figure 3b, it was observed that the presence of CPA improved the density of the compacted mixture by an increase from 2259kg/m³ at 0% CPA to 2277kg/m³ at 7.5% CPA for none submergence period, 2256kg/m³ at 0% CPA to 2274kg/m³ at 7.5% CPA for 1 day submergence period, 2249kg/m³ at 0% CPA to 2267kg/m³ at 7.5% CPA for 2 days submergence period, 2242kg/m³ at 0% CPA to 2260kg/m³ at 7.5% CPA for 3 days submergence period, 2239kg/m³ at 0% CPA to 2257kg/m³ at 7.5% CPA for 4 days submergence period and 2229kg/m³ at 0% CPA to 2247kg/m³ at 7.5% CPA for

Density of compacted asphalt concrete mixture indicates the level of compaction achieved and correlates strongly with pavement service life (Mogawer *et al.*, 2011). The graphs shown in figures 3a to 3b represent the density of the asphalt concrete mixture modified with CPA and submerged in water for a period of 0 to 5 day(s).

Fig. 3b: Effect of CPA on density.

5 days submergence period. The density improvement indicates denser particle packing, which minimizes air voids and enhances load transfer. The subsequent decline at higher CPA content could lead to particle agglomeration and insufficient binder for coating (Ongel & Hugener, 2015). Furthermore, it was observed that the presence of CPA improved the density of the compacted mixture by a slight margin of approximately 0.8% as compared to the control, for all CPA modified samples submerged in water. Also, the density of all CPA modified samples fell within the recommended range of 2200kg/m³ to 2500kg/m³ (Tarefder & Makar, 2015; ASTM D2726-17, 2017).

Effect of CPA Content on Air Voids

Air voids represent the interstitial air pockets present within a dense asphalt concrete matrix, with their proportion being paramount to the efficacy of

pavement performance. Figures 4a and 4b represent the response of air voids to moisture submergence and CPA modification of asphalt concrete mixtures

Fig. 4a: Effect of submergence on air voids.

Figure 4a depicts a progressive increase in air voids with increase in immersion time. Previous studies have revealed that water immersion accelerates stripping of the mixture by the loss of adhesive bonding ability of the aggregate and the binder films, resulting in density reduction and increased permeability; giving rise to increased air voids and which leads to pavement degradation (Jasim & Jon, 2022). On the other hand, figure 4b shows a decrease of air voids from 4.42% at 0% CPA to 3.27% at 7.5% CPA for none submergence period, 4.45% at 0% CPA to 3.37% at 7.5% CPA for 1 day submergence period, 4.75% at 0% CPA to 3.60% at 7.5% CPA for 2 days submergence period, 4.98% at 0% CPA to 3.83% at 7.5% CPA for 3 days submergence period, 5.08% at 0% CPA to 3.93% at 7.5% CPA for 4 days submergence period and 5.40% at 0% CPA to 4.27% at 7.5% CPA for 5 days submergence period. This reduction in air voids is a signal of a better filler distribution from the CPA content and an improved aggregate interlock. Beyond 7.5% CPA content, the air voids began to

immersed in water for a period of 0 to 5 day(s).

Fig. 4b: Effect of CPA on air voids.

increase, which indicates loss of cohesion and higher voids associated with excessive CPA content (Akinyemi & Olatunji, 2014; Ettu *et al.*, 2013). It was observed that the presence of CPA in the mixture improved the air voids by approximately 20.93-26.02% as compared to the control, for all CPA modified samples submerged in water. Also, the values of air voids for all CPA modified samples fell within the range of 3% to 5% for up to 4 days submergence, in accordance with Marshall criteria, as indicated in table 1 above.

Effect of CPA Content on Voids in Mineral Aggregate (VMA)

Voids in Mineral Aggregates (VMA) is a volumetric parameter representing the inter-granular void space between the aggregate particles in a compacted asphalt concrete mixture, which is filled with bitumen and air, excluding aggregate internal pore spaces. Figures 5a to 5b represents the response of VMA to moisture submergence and CPA modification of asphalt concrete mixtures immersed in water for a period of 0 to 5 day(s).

Fig. 5a: Effect of submergence on VMA.

Figure 5a reveals a progressive increase in VMA with increase in the period of submergence. Previous studies has revealed that water immersion accelerates stripping of the mixture by the loss of adhesive bonding ability of the aggregate and the binder films, resulting in density reduction and increased permeability; giving rise to increased air voids and which leads to pavement degradation (Jasim & Joni, 2022). On the other hand, figure 5b shows a decrease of air voids from 13.70% at 0% CPA to 13.20% at 7.5% CPA for none submergence period, 13.79% at 0% CPA to 13.28% at 7.5% CPA for 1 day submergence period, 13.98% at 0% CPA to 13.48% at 7.5% CPA for 2 days submergence period, 14.18% at 0% CPA to 13.68% at 7.5% CPA for 3 days submergence period, 14.27% at 0% CPA to 13.77% at 7.5% CPA for 4 days submergence period and 14.55% at 0% CPA to 14.06% at 7.5% CPA for 5 days submergence period. This reduction in air voids is a signal of a better filler distribution from the CPA content and an improved aggregate interlock. At further addition of CPA content, the VMA

Fig. 5b: Effect of CPA on VMA.

began to increase, which indicates loss of cohesion and higher voids associated with excessive CPA content (Akinyemi & Olatunji, 2014; Ettu *et al.*, 2013). It was also observed that the presence of CPA in the mixture improved the VMA by approximately 3.37 - 3.70% as compared to the control, for all CPA modified samples submerged in water, and that the VMA values for all samples ranges within 13% to 15%, in accordance with standard specification as indicated in table 2 and table 4.

Effect of CPA Content on Voids Filled with Asphalt (VFA)

Voids Filled with Asphalt (VFA) is a crucial volumetric parameter that indicates the percentage of the voids in the mineral aggregate (VMA) that are filled with asphalt. It reflects how much binder is available to coat and fill aggregate voids. Figures 6a to 6b represents the response of voids filled with asphalt to moisture submergence and CPA modification of asphalt concrete mixtures submerged in water for a period of 0 to 5 day(s).

Fig. 6a: Effect of submergence on VFA.

Figure 6a shows a progressive decrease in VFA of the compacted asphalt concrete mixtures, with increase in submergence period for all CPA modified samples, conforming to the outcome from previous studies (Indriani *et al.*, 2024). This is so because it has been proven that moisture infiltrates asphalt pavements through air voids, weakening the asphalt–aggregate bond and reducing mixture density, hence leading to decrease in VFA (Fernandes *et al.*, 2017). However, from figure 6b, it was observed that the presence of CPA improved the VFA of the compacted mixture by an increase from 67.71% at 0% CPA to 75.23% at 7.5% CPA for none submergence period, 67.20% at 0% CPA to 74.64% at 7.5% CPA for 1 day submergence period, 66.03% at 0% CPA to 73.30% at 7.5% CPA for 2 days submergence period, 64.89% at 0% CPA to 71.99% at 7.5% CPA for 3 days submergence period, 64.42% at 0% CPA to 71.44% at 7.5% CPA for 4 days submergence period and 62.86% at 0% CPA to 69.65% at 7.5% CPA for 5 days submergence period. This indicates optimal binder coating and resistance to moisture damage. The subsequent reduction at 10% CPA reflects poor binder distribution and the onset of mix segregation. Furthermore, it was observed that the inclusion of CPA into the mixture improved the VFA by approximately 10.80 - 11.11% as compared to the control,

Fig. 6b: Effect of CPA on VFA.

for all CPA modified samples submerged in water, and all CPA modified samples fell within the range of 65% to 75% for all sample modified with CPA, in accordance with Marshall criteria, as indicated in table 1 above.

CONCLUSION

This study assessed the influence of cassava peel ash (CPA) as a mineral filler on the Bruce Marshall properties of asphalt concrete under submergence. The following conclusions were drawn:

- i. Incorporating CPA improved all Marshall properties under submergence up to an optimal replacement level of 7.5%.
- ii. Across all parameters, 7.5% CPA consistently yielded the most favorable balance of stability, density, flow, and volumetric properties; with an overall improvement of approximately: 49.34 - 59.60% in stability, 9% in flow, 0.8% in density, 20.93 - 26.02% in air voids (V_a), 3.37 - 3.7% in voids in mineral aggregates (VMA) and 10.80 - 11.11% in voids filled with asphalt (VFA) as compared to the control mix. The improvement at this level is attributed to:
 - Pozzolanic reaction between CPA oxides and asphalt binder components.
 - Increased matrix densification reducing water susceptibility.

- Enhanced adhesion and stiffness due to fine particle interaction.
- iii. Beyond 7.5% CPA, stability, density and VFA decreased while air voids and VMA increased due to excess ash leading to binder absorption and reduced cohesion.
- iv. The use of CPA offers a sustainable and cost-effective alternative to traditional fillers while addressing agricultural waste disposal issues.
- v. Further research is recommended to assess the long-term aging and rutting resistance of CPA-modified mixes under cyclic submergence conditions.

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